

Modeling the Generation of Cochlear Microphonics Potentials at the Round Window: Effect of Higher Dimensionality

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Abstract. The cochlear microphonic (CM) potentials measured at the round window (RWCM) are primarily generated by outer hair cells (OHCs) located in the tail region of the traveling wave. However, recent experiments have shown that contributions from the peak region might be measurable. The RWCM has been typically modeled based on a 1D theory, in which the scala tympani (ST) is represented by a longitudinal electrical cable. This work aims to demonstrate the limitations of 1D cable models and to improve understanding of RWCM generation. A two-dimensional (2D) finite element model (FEM) that takes into account both the longitudinal and transverse variations of the CM is coupled to a previously developed physiologically motivated cochlear model in order to predict the CM in the ST in response to acoustic stimulation. The local cochlear microphonics (LCM), *i.e.*, the CM predicted near the basilar membrane (BM) by the 2D model, decays quickly away from the BM in the peak region, as observed *in vivo*. The tuning curve of the LCM response is much more similar in shape to *in vivo* experiments in the 2D model than in the 1D cable model. Furthermore, the contributions from OHCs located near the peak of the traveling wave are found to be non-negligible in the 2D model. This work improves understanding of CM generation which is important for characterizing the electromechanical feedback from OHCs and for the noninvasive evaluation of cochlear function using RWCM measurements.

INTRODUCTION

The cochlear microphonic (CM) is an AC electrical potential primarily generated by outer hair cells (OHCs) [1]. It can be measured at different locations, including inside the scala tympani (ST) [2], or at the round window. Measurements of the CM at the round window (which we will denote RWCM throughout this article) are noninvasive to the cochlea, and provide a method to monitor OHC function. However, the RWCM primarily originates from OHCs located at the base of the cochlea. Contributions from OHCs located at more apical locations are expected to be more limited due to electrical attenuation and to cancellation from sources within the region of short wavelength near the traveling wave (TW) peak. However, recent experiments have shown that the use of alternative stimuli (*i.e.*, two-tone stimuli) and processing methodology may be used to extract information from more apical locations using RWCM [3, 4]. There is still limited understanding of how apically located OHCs may contribute to RWCM.

Strelioff developed an electrical network model of the CM of the cochlea that represents each cochlear duct as a one-dimensional (1D) longitudinal electrical cable [5]. That model, which was calibrated based on data obtained by placing electrodes within the cochlear ducts, has space constants (which characterize the exponential decay of the CM away from a current source) of a few thousand micrometers. Measurements of RWCM residuals in response to a two-tone stimulus also suggest that the space constant is of the order of few thousands of micrometers [4]. However, cable models that have been fitted based on measurements of the local CM (LCM), *i.e.* the CM measurements near the basilar membrane (BM) in the scala tympani (ST) suggest that electrical longitudinal coupling is much weaker, with much smaller space constants of 40 to 150 μm [2, 6]. This apparent discrepancy may be due to the limitations of 1D cable theory, which is unable to account for the spatial variations observed in more accurate models and experiments. Recent three-dimensional (3D) finite element models (FEMs) [7, 8] have shown that the CM in the ST does not behave in the same way as in 1D cable models. Both experiments and 3D model simulations show that the CM decays away from the BM, which the 1D model does not account for.

In this article, we aim to study how higher dimensionality affects the key characteristics of the CM, especially at the RW. We couple a two-dimensional (2D) model of the CM in the ST to our existing physiologically motivated model of the cochlea [9]. We use this model to study the spatial variations of the CM and to examine the contributions from the OHCs located near the peak of the TW to the RWCM.

FIGURE 1. Schematic of the 1D (A) and 2D (B) electrical models of the CM in ST. x and z are the longitudinal and transverse directions, respectively. The MET current, i_{MET} , depends nonlinearly on the HB deflection. The potential across the OHC wall, $\Delta V_{ohc}(x) = V_{ohc}(x) - V_{st}(x, z = 0)$, gives rise to the electromotile force $f_{som}(x)$. In the 1D model, the scala vestibuli, scala media, ST are represented as electrical longitudinal cables. In the 2D model, only the scala vestibuli and scala media are represented as longitudinal cables; the ST is represented by a 2D finite element model. The current from the OHC, $i_{ohc}(x)$, serves as a line source for the 2D finite element model of the CM in the ST. The outer wall (OW) has a lower conductivity than the ST. The voltage at the bottom of the OW is set to 0.

METHODS

The model is based on our previously developed physiologically motivated model of the cochlea, which predicts the vibrations of organ of Corti structures, the intracochlear fluid pressure, and the electrical potential in the cochlear ducts and OHCs in response to acoustic stimulation [9]. The electrical domain of the previous model is based on longitudinal cables in the scala vestibuli, scala media, and ST (see Fig. 1A). In the current work, a 2D FEM of the voltage in the ST replaces the 1D longitudinal cable model (Fig. 1B).

The cochlear model predicts the OHC current, $I_{ohc}(x)$, which then acts as a line source for the FEM model of the CM in the ST, in a manner similar to the model from Frost and Olson [8]. The charge continuity equation and Ohm's law can be combined to yield the following equation within the ST and outer wall (OW):

$$\sigma(x, z) \nabla^2 V = 0 \quad (1)$$

where $V(x, z)$ is the voltage and $\sigma(x, z)$ is the conductance, which is equal to σ_{ST} in the ST ($-H < z < 0$, where H is the height of the ST) and to $\sigma_{ow} = \sigma_{ST}/K$ in the OW ($-H + H_{ow} < z < -H$) where K is a constant. The value of σ_{ST} controls the overall amplitude of the CM response while K affects the locality of the CM response and the shape of the LCM response (see [8]). All results with the 2D model are obtained with $K = 5$ and $\sigma_{ST} = 21.8$ mS/cm. Eq. 1 along with the boundary conditions at $z = 0$, $z = -H$, $z = -(H + H_{ow})$ are solved using the finite element method.

FIGURE 2. Spatial response in response to 23 kHz 30 dB SPL tone. A. Normalized amplitude of BM displacement and OHC current. B. Product of wavenumber times height of the duct. C. Surface plot of the voltage in the ST for low SPL tone. D. Amplitude of the CM response vs x at different distance from the BM.

RESULTS

Intracochlear response

We first examine the response of the model to a low-level pure tone (30 dB SPL) of frequency 23 kHz as a function of position (Fig. 2). The response of the BM and the OHC current are first plotted in Fig. 2A. The OHC current is especially important as it is the current source that drives the CM in the ST. Due to the detailed micromechanics of the organ of Corti and of the electrical model of the OHCs in our physiologically motivated cochlear model, the OHC current and the BM are similarly but not identically tuned. The wavenumber, k , was calculated from the phase of the OHC current and is plotted in Fig. 2B. As observed in the intracochlear fluid pressure (*e.g.* [10, 11]), kH (the product of the wavenumber and of the height of the ST duct) dictates the type of the electrical response in the CM in the 2D model. In the basal long wave region where kH is small, the CM varies little as the distance from the BM increases (Fig. 2C); in the short wave region near the best place where kH is large, the CM response decays quickly as the distance from the BM increases. Because of these spatial variations, the CM has a tuned response if measured near the BM, but becomes progressively less tuned as the distance from the BM is increased (Fig. 2D).

Figure 3 shows the nonlinear response of the model vs. frequency at the location tuned to 23 kHz. The BM displacement has a nonlinear response around the best frequency (Fig. 3A). As in the experiments (Fig. 3D), the LCM predicted by the 1D model (Fig. 3B) has a nonlinear response that extends significantly below the BF of 23 kHz. However, the shape of the response differs from the experimental results shown in Fig. 3D. The LCM predicted near the BM by the 2D model (Fig. 3C) has a shape that resembles the experimental results. This includes the presence of a notch near 18 kHz at stimulus level below 60 dB SPL, and the lowpass nature of the LCM response at stimulus levels up to 70 dB SPL.

FIGURE 3. Pure tone response of the model at the 23 kHz best place: BM and LCM response. A. and E. Amplitude and phase of BM displacement relative to ear canal pressure, P_{ec} . B. and F. Amplitude and phase LCM response predicted by the 1D electrical model. C. and G. LCM response predicted directly next the BM by the 2D model ($0 \mu\text{m}$ from the BM). D and H. Amplitude and phase of LCM at about $10 \mu\text{m}$ from the BM in gerbil experiments from Ref. [6]. All amplitudes are relative to ear canal pressure.

Response at the round window: contributions from OHCs located near the peak

We focus next on the RWCM response, *i.e.*, the CM response at $x = 0$. The RWCM predicted by the 1D and 2D models are somewhat similar if contributions from all OHCs are considered (the blue lines in Fig. 4C-D), although the 2D model predicts a RWCM about 5-10 dB higher than the 1D model. The amplitude of the RWCM is in the same range as experiments in gerbil (about $1 \mu\text{V}$ at 30 dB SPL in [12]). However, the contributions from OHCs located near the peak of the TW are much lower in the 1D model than the 2D model. This can be demonstrated by eliminating the contributions from basal OHCs in the CM model by setting I_{ohc} to 0 in the region that extends from the base ($x = 0$) to a location slightly basal to the peak location (80% of the x value of the frequency-dependent best place). It is useful to first examine the CM in the ST vs. x , shown in Fig. 4A-B. In the 1D model, the CM decays quickly at locations basal to the border of the region where the contributions from OHCs are eliminated (indicated by the vertical dotted line in Fig. 4A), and drops quickly below -20 dB. This implies that, the total CM predicted at the base by the 1D model (*i.e.*, the blue line in Fig. 4A) are locally generated by basal OHCs. The small amplitude CM predicted at the base by the 1D model without basal contributions, which are non-local contributions that originate from OHCs located near the peak, are negligible in the 1D model. However, in the 2D model (Fig. 4B), the CM in the ST remains above -10 dB within the region where $I_{ohc} = 0$. This indicates that OHCs located near the peak contribute to the CM measured at the base, including at the RW. This is confirmed in Fig. 4D, where the red line shows the response of the model without basal contributions. While the RWCM predicted by the model without basal contributions becomes smaller as the frequency is reduced, it remains above -45 dB at all frequencies. In contrast to these results, the 1D model shows that the RWCM predicted by the model without basal contributions drops below -80 dB at frequencies below approximately 30 kHz (Fig. 4C).

It is also interesting to note that the notch observed in the total LCM in Fig. 4B, which is the correlate of the notch in the plot vs. frequency in Fig. 3C, disappears when basal OHC contributions are eliminated. This implies that this notch is the result of cancellation between contributions from basal OHCs and from OHCs located near the peak.

FIGURE 4. A and B. CM in the ST predicted by the 1D model (A) and the 2D model near the BM (B) in response to a 30 dB SPL 23 kHz tone. C and D. RWCM predicted by the 1D model (C) and the 2D model (D). In all panels, the blue line corresponds to the response of the model that includes contributions from all OHCs; the red line corresponds to the response of the model where basal OHC contributions have been eliminated by setting I_{ohc} to 0 in the shaded region (which extend from $x = 0$ to 80% of the x location of the best place).

DISCUSSION

In a 1D model, the strength of electrical longitudinal coupling only depends on the space constant. It is impossible in these models to represent with high fidelity the very local response of the LCM (which would require a short space constant of 10s of μm) while simultaneously accounting from the apparent strong coupling in some aspects of the RWCM [4, 13] (which would require a long space constant of thousands of μm). Models of higher dimensionality, such as the 2D model considered here, are required to properly capture the key characteristics of the LCM and RWCM with a single set of parameters. The current model is based on a 2D model of the ST voltage, which may not be as accurate as 3D finite element models [7, 8]. However, as observed in the case of the fluid hydrodynamics, the improvement in accuracy when switching from a 1D to 2D model is much more significant than what is expected when switching from a 2D to a 3D model. The use of a 2D model allows us to capture one of the key characteristics that the 1D model fails to account for, *i.e.*, the localization of the ST voltage response close to the OHC current source. This localization of the CM response has been observed in experiments and predicted by a 3D finite element model of the ST voltage [8].

The numerical results obtained with the 2D model show that, even though the RWCM originates primarily from OHCs located near the base, the RWCM includes small but potentially measurable contributions from the OHCs located near the peak of the TW. This model will be used as a computational tool to investigate how RWCM measurements may be used to assess OHC function using for example two tone distortion products [3], suppression residuals [4], and spectral ripples resulting from the interaction of multiple components [14].

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COMMENTS AND DISCUSSION

[Chris Shera] Thank you for this fascinating paper. Perhaps you can clarify something for me and comment on it in the paper. If I understand the model (and Fig. 3) correctly, then it appears that the BM response does not depend on the dimensionality of the ST electrical domain. In other words, the BM responses of the new cochlear model (2D electrical domain in ST) are the same as those in the previous model (1D cable). I say this because panels A and E do not specify the dimensionality. Is this true? And is it true of all mechanical responses in the model, not just that of the BM? Or, if it's not true, then how does the assumed dimensionality of the electrical domain affect the motion of the BM and other structures? Or perhaps the mechanical and electrical domains in the model are not bidirectionally coupled?

[Julien Meaud] Thank you for this excellent question and for providing us the opportunity to clarify this point. It is true that there is no bidirectional coupling in the current model with 2D electrical domain. For the results shown in the paper, we used the following approach: 1) the cochlear model with 1D electrical domain is used to predict the OHC current; 2) the OHC current is then used as a line source in the 2D model of the cochlear microphonics of the ST. Because the mechanical response of the model depends on the OHC current (since this is an active model), we are making the approximation that the dimensionality of the electrical domain does not affect the OHC current. We believe this is a good approximation for the following reasons. The OHC current depends on the difference between the intracellular potential of the OHC, V_{ohc} and the potential in the ST, V_{st} (according to the electrical circuit of Fig. 1). Because V_{ohc} is predicted to be about 2 orders of magnitude higher than V_{st} in both the 1D and 2D model, the dimensionality of the electrical domain is not expected to have a significant effect on the OHC current, such that it is not expected to affect significantly the mechanical response. This is something we intend to verify once we implement the 2D electrical domain in a model with bidirectional coupling, which we intend to do.

[Jont Allen]: Is the cochlear microphonics proportional to displacement of basilar membrane or something else like the velocity?

[Julien Meaud]: In the model, the cochlear microphonics is proportional to the electrical current, which depends on the hair bundle deflection, which is neither proportional to BM displacement or velocity, but depends on the mechanical response of the BM, tectorial membrane, and reticular lamina.

[Jont Allen]: My answer is that the stereocilia of the OHCs are plugged in the tectorial membrane, so that they are responding to some kind of differential displacement or movement of the tectorial membrane relative to the BM. So they respond to some form of displacement.

[Julien Meaud]: I agree with the first part – they depend on the relative displacement of the tectorial membrane.

[Jont Allen]: what would happen if you cut off the oxygen to the animal while you measure the cochlear microphonics? I know the answer because I did the experiment.

[Julien Meaud]: I would expect the RWCM to drop.

[Jont Allen]: the CM drops to 0 within 30s in my experiments and then within 1 min I turned the oxygen back on and within an hour it returns to normal.

[Anders Fridberger]: Another common use of the round window cochlear microphonics is to use an intense and very low frequency stimulus to gauge the operating point of the hair cells. In that situation, would you think that the potential you record mostly comes from hair cells close to the electrodes, or could there be contributions from more apical hair cells also?

[Julien Meaud]: I would think it would come from the most basal hair cells located close to the electrodes, but I should look more into these papers – these sound interesting.